

Paradigm Shift in English Language Pedagogy of Secondary Level: From Conventional to Modern

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims at exploration of English language paradigm shift from conventional to modern in terms of curricular focus, methodology, evaluation practice, teachers and learners behavior. Based upon the existing literature, critical analysis has been done to explore how changes in pedagogical context happened from traditional structured approach to post modern perspective. These changes are reflected in present days teaching learning ecology in secondary school. It was found that there is paradigm shift in English pedagogy from teacher centrism, structuralism, behaviorism to learner centered, post modern and constructive approach. This transition in English language pedagogy is a result of revolutionary process of change in society and academic world. Academicians and practitioners will be benefited from this thematic paper.

Key words: Paradigm shift, English language, Pedagogy

INTRODUCTION

English as a school subject in the secondary education in India occupies an important place in the school curriculum. It has the value for connecting with people throughout world, a language of trade and commerce, language of library and medium of instruction in higher education (Graddol, 2006, Murata & Jenkis, 2009). Competency in English language is also associated with scientific temperament, wider opportunity, increased power and prestige as well as symbol of progresses (Amin, 2016). But, there is a fear among the students for English language in India which is reflected in terms of their poor English language skills and lower achievement. The problem of English language learning among students is directly linked with English language teaching and learning. English as a school subject of India is taught to students in the similar ways like other school subjects (Baloch, 2014). Sometimes, taught by the teachers who are not an English teacher. This pedagogical shortcoming or use of inappropriate pedagogy is one of the reasons for lower English language skill acquisition and achievement which is directly related with English teacher's knowledge about pedagogy, their context of use and perspectives. It has been found that English teacher's in India have less knowledge about various teaching methods to teach English and their context of application. This thematic work has been organized in three primary sections, i.e. the traditional or classical methods, modern methods and transformation from traditional to modern methods.

Historical Perspective of English Language Teaching in India:

English as a school subject in India has its historical root in Macaulay's minute where the intention of English teaching for Indian students was to produce a class of Indian who will be Indian by blood but taste in English and help for British administration. As a result, English was taught primarily by grammar translation method and the content of syllabus was primarily based on European literature. Development of oral linguistic skills such as listening and speaking were least focused. But reading ability among students was given priority, with an objective that it may help to read English texts, but not helpful for development of oral communication skills (Pinke, 2018). Along with this Grammar translation method, audio-lingual and direct methods were also used to

teach English (Pica, 2000). This pedagogical method and western world culture syllabi- content of English teaching is till now practicing in India.

Traditional English Pedagogy, practice and Context

Traditionally, English as a school subject in India was taught primarily by Grammar-translation, Direct and Audio-lingual methods. Grammar translation as a method of English pedagogy has historical context of use in the western world countries. In 14th century, there was a demand in Europe for translation of European classical language to English. In 1536, Bible was translated to English which was original in Greek language (Sawant, 2013; Dave and Joshi, 2018). Chaucer who was known as father of English literature had translated one famous French epic to English in 14th century. The works of Dante and Homer were translated to English during that period, which signifies that Grammar translation method as popular in Western world countries during 16th century, especially to teach English to the non native English language students. Grammar translation as a method of English teaching is based on structural theories of language where it is assumed that language is consist of structures and grammatical elements and knowing the language means knowing these structures and grammatical rules. The technique of teaching in this method is translation of English to native language or vice-versa. The learning techniques for this method is drilling, exercise and practice (Machida, 2011).

Although this method is till date used globally but more popular in the countries where student's native language is not English. This method has advantages for fewer requirements of teaching-learning materials, economical and scope to advancement of vocabulary among students (Kirkpatrick, 2010). At the same time, this method has limitations from linguistic skill development point of view. Excessive focus on grammar rules, vocabulary and language structure during teaching and less focus on development of linguistic skills, i.e. listening and speaking, hampers student's communication skills. Secondly, use of this method is inappropriate for every situation and context, especially when the meaning of a particular word has different contextual meaning, its exact translation is not possible. In this pedagogical method, there is minimum scope for oral expression. As this method excessively emphasis on the grammatical and structural rules of English and less on its use, the semantic and pragmatic aspect were ignored (Gillanders, 2007; Xu & Drame, 2008). Although ideally, it is expected to give equal emphasis on both languages during translation method (target and medium) but it was found that teachers give more emphasis

on native language and less on target language which results poor language skill achievement among students in target language.

Along with use of this pedagogy for teaching English, it is found that Direct method was also used traditionally in India and globally.

Direct method aims at establishing direct association between thought and expressions through experiences of the learner. It supports the assumption that there will be experience of the new language (English) in the same way in which learner experienced the native language. The learner begins to think in English and gets an active command over the language. Here, fluency in reading and facility in writing follow the fluency in speech. The first step of leaning a language is learning to speak the language first, which is the basic principle of this method. The 'input before output' approach was placed as listening prior to speaking (Richard & Rodgers, 2001). The assumption of Direct Method is that, a second language can be learnt in exactly the same way as a first language. So the learning experiences are given directly in the target language during the time of instruction to the learners. More exposure to English is given to the learners to develop oral fluency and spontaneity.

Direct method is also called natural method because the learner directly use the target language to communicate, derive meanings of words, phrases and idioms with the help of teachers' action and demonstration during classroom practices (Batool et al., 2017). In this method, grammar or language structure is less focused to learn grammar rules during the teaching learning process through illustrations, demonstration and audio-visual aids. This method is found to be more effective for secondary school students (Hussain et al., 2009). Meanings of any text/ word/sentence is made clear by presentation of physical objects and abstract ones through association of thoughts and ideas, not through direct translation. Sound or the phonetic parts of language is given much emphasis is presented in the classroom (Setiyadi, 2020). The pedagogical mechanics in this method are demonstration, visual illustrations, miming, contextualization and activities. Sufficient emphasis is given to associate meanings of sentences and their practical use by students (Adebileje and Akinola, 2020).

This language based pedagogy has limitations in terms of excess use of resources and teaching learning materials which are expensive (Batool et al., 2017). It requires highly competent teacher

who is good in the target language which is a major problem in India. This method gives much emphasis on teacher than the text book. The assumption of direct instruction and deriving meaning is by simply listening to or reading texts do not fulfill always in case of English as a second language in India as some meaning of word or text has contextual meaning which varies from situation to situation. As a result, pedagogical experts suggest for another method which has the capacity to overcome limitation of direct method.

During outbreak of World War-II, there was a demand in America for such Army official who would be proficient speakers of various foreign languages which leads deign a foreign language learning approach by the American Universities. The learning approach was Aural-oral and the mechanism was hearing and specking. The learner will learn a foreign language by hearing the ways a native speaker talks and then practicing to speak in that same way. So in this context observation, imitation, drill/practice is very much important. This method was popular in the spain to learn English and other European countries primarily required to gain competency to speak like native speaker as opportunity may come to work in that country. From psychological basis, it can be mentioned that this method of language acquisition is based on Behaviorism. Academicians claim that foreign languages can be taught in this method in the same way as habits formation through the process of conditioning or training (Shameem, 2013). As language learning is a matter of habit formation, i.e. stronger habit leads to greater learning of language (Paudel, 2020).

This method is based on the assumption that language mastery can be achieved through habit formation or stimulus-response connection chains and proper habit formation on the target language. The sub cognitive skills for this foreign language learning are sound recognition, discrimination, imitation, repetition and memorization. Dialogue or speech is the core of audio-lingual pedagogy and sufficient time is allotted for repetition and memorization of the dialogue. This method uses drills and pattern practice which includes free response, directed discourse, substitution, transformation, repetition and expansion of dialogues or content through listening and speaking (Karunakaran, 2013). In this method, students interact intensively with the native speakers and a linguist in guided conversations primarily designed to decode its basic grammar and learn the essential vocabulary (Richards and Rodgers, 2001).

Though this method has contextual application for learning a foreign language as spoken by the native speaker but use of this pedagogical method requires native speaker as tutor which is not

always possible to have. Secondly, use of this method in the class room is directly dependent upon the need for use of that language by the learner. For example, in India English is taught as a second language which the student will use as co-official language within India.

From a synthetic perspective on conventional or traditional pedagogical approach used, it can be stated that as these pedagogical methods are based on Behavioristic psychology which primarily follows the PPP technique, i.e. 'present', 'practice', and 'produce'. As these methods gives emphasis on the repeated tasks of reading, reading aloud, memorization, and other kinds of form-focused practices, it causes classroom learning monotonous, less interesting and less effective for learning (Wang and Hill, 2011). But these methods have contextual application in teaching English where the main focus of learning language is to learn 'language points' i.e. the words, phrases, and structures of language which are crucial in language teaching for meaning processing and reading comprehension (Dahlin & Watkins, 2000; Ellis, 2008). Chen and Ying (2009) has claimed that the traditional practices of language have a significant effect on development of fluency and comprehension among learners but the mechanical repetition of learning materials does not help for meaningful communication. This suboptimal and rudimentary functioning of methods in varied language contexts lead to search for a balanced pedagogy which can address every aspect of language learning i.e. communicative, competence and pragmatic. As a result innovations in language pedagogy emerged by integrating all aspects of language learning in its various forms as well as terrain.

Innovations and modern pedagogy in ELT with theoretical context

In this globalized scenario, there is a constant need for innovation. The research on innovation in language teaching began to generate interest from the 1980s onwards as a result of dynamics and challenges of implementing educational reform which were often overlooked and inadequately addressed before that period. In recent decades, innovation is been a greater significance especially in language education as evidenced by recent books: Murray, (2008), Alderson (2009), and Wedell (2009). Carless (2018) in his study defined innovation as an attempt to bring about educational improvement by doing something which is perceived by implementers (teachers and practitioners) as new or different. Fatiloro (2015) argues that the lack of a variety of teaching methods, techniques create a hindrance for learning English as a second language. To bring varieties in learning and for better language learning outcome the innovations in methods, strategies and approaches are the

accelerating agents. For Indian context, the litany of language educational policy failures suggests application of innovative methods in English teaching from school level (Das, 2022).

Now days, the most substantive changes also are made in English language teaching through a collection of classroom practices, teaching learning materials and beliefs about teaching and learning process which integrates variations in content and context of language teaching (Pica, 2000). The classroom pedagogy shifted to more on communicative language teaching. This approach represents a philosophy of teaching that is based on using language for communicative purpose in its appropriate context. It emphasizes on the functional use of language components and communicative competence rather than using grammatical structures and patterns as central to teaching learning process.

Communicative approaches to language teaching:

With the introduction of communicative language teaching (CLT), the perspective of language teaching experienced considerable changes as per the nature and context of language. There are various features of communicative approach which integrates multiple language skills to be practiced at once which helps learner to communicate effectively (Hinkel, 2006; Zacharias, 2013). This approach focuses on the philosophy of teaching that is based on communicative language use. The central to teaching is the notional (concepts such as time, sequence; quantity, location, and frequency) and functional concepts (requests, offers, complaints, invitations etc.) and also communicative competence (linguistic, socio-linguistic, discourse and strategic) rather than grammatical structures. This method primarily follows three principles named as; communication principle, tasks principle and meaningfulness principle (Richards & Rodgers, 2000) and the classroom activities, learners involvement goes accordingly. Various activities that involve communication to promote learning, completion of language tasks, classroom discourse and learner engagement in meaningful and authentic language contexts is the key classroom techniques to promote communicative learning. Communicative language teaching continues in the range of varieties of course books and teaching resources based on the principles of CLT. The classroom techniques are role play, interview, problem solving, language game, conversation, pair and group activities, debate and discussion, opinion and comments, narration, dialogues and reporting etc. This method is more learner centric capitalizing the need and interest of learners and provides vitality of motivation in classroom.

Despite of massive popularity, communicative language teaching experiences some drawbacks in terms of learners' resistance and difficulties in implementation particularly in India and other Asian countries (Kumaravadivelu 2006) and ineffective in non-Western contexts for lack of conducive ecology (Nunan 1999). Due to its focus on producing native-like proficiency among language learners has also been criticized for being insensitive to learners' own cultural identity to some extent (Byram 1997). Finally, CLT method fails to incorporate the social and pragmatic component of language learning to utmost (Bax, 2003). Because of these apprehensions, more transitions occur in the field of English language teaching.

Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT)

Task-based language teaching (TBLT) has been introduced since the 1980s. It was explored as the alternative pedagogical tool as an extension form of CLT (Skehan 1996, Barrot, 2013). Task based language teaching refers to the activities in target language i.e English by which learners can learn and produce the language fluently. This method of teaching is conceptualized differently on the basis of variations in tasks. Scholars believe this TBLT is the incorporation of various methods and principles, such as information processing theories, collaborative learning, and interactionist hypothesis specially introduced to develop learners' second language knowledge and skills (Long and Crookes 1992).

In this pedagogy, several language tasks are assigned to learners in which they have interest and complete the assigned task (Richard and Rogers, 2020). These language tasks are based on principles of meaningful, communicative in nature and contextualized application. Learners are engaged in these language tasks in its use such as; information gap activities, reasoning, comprehending, interacting, manipulating and producing the second language which allows students to exchange information and learn things by conversation with each other. For communication learners are allowed to interact and gain personal experience not only in the classroom but also outside. The primary goal of TBLT to promote language acquisition along the three dimensions of fluency, accuracy and complexity. Here, the achievement of goal varies learner to learner as their cognitive skills differ one to another. In order to cope with this problem some authors (e.g. Skehan, 1996) suggested three types of language tasks in a sequence i.e. *pre-task*, *during-task*, *post-task*. The pre-task begins with sequencing and introducing the language needed for task performance, during- task takes place after the task is selected and it allows the

learners to be engaged in fulfilling the goals of the language task, post-task activities deal with refining what has been learnt.

TBLT like all communicative approaches, tries to recreate natural learning conditions in the classroom, the reason is that natural conditions are assumed to be ideal for learning a language. Here, the issue is whether 'natural conditions' can be recreated in the classroom. If, the assigned kind of tasks can work within the classroom are very different from the real world tasks. Many academicians criticized TBLT saying it does not seem to be based on new learning principles; rather it offers simply a novel way of being exposed to and practices the language just by involving and motivating the student. This novel way is considered as the task by which the learner learning is supposed to be effective (Sanchez, 2004).

Technology mediated Task-Based Language Teaching:

With globalization and advancement of technology, the language classroom pedagogy have also enriched in terms of methods, techniques, learning resources and learner engagement (Brown, 2002). Based on the basic principles of TBLT, technology mediated tasks are meaningful, goal oriented, authentic, communicative in nature and activity based. The first technology mediated task was program based language learning on computer-assisted language learning (CALL) which helped learners to engage to drill, train, and test language skills (Andone & Frydenberg, 2019). The tasks included such as jigsaw, information gap activities, discussion (both open-ended and close-ended) etc. Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is believed to be effective because it decreases educational costs and increases leaning outcomes for a long period (Atabek, 2020; Oz, Demirezen, & Pourfeiz, 2015). However, the effectiveness of CALL is affected by some moderators such as learners, task type, educational settings and conditions and the assessment instruments (Sadeghi & Dousti, 2013).

Lloret and Ortega (2014) opined technology mediated TBLT as the integration of technology and tasks in teaching learning process. With the aim of achieving communicative competence and technology utilization within learners, TMTBLT is seen as an alternative method to the traditional English teaching method. This method offer students the chance to engage in a more meaningful individualized learning process through tasks and assignments that teachers can flexibly adapt integrating the communicative and communal qualities. Aligning with this view Lloret and Ortega

(2014) propose five principles of TMTBLT: (1) meaning-oriented (2) a clearly defined language learning outcome (3) the task should adapt resources as per students' needs (4) the task should be authentic in nature and (5) tasks should involve maximum engagement in tasks to learners in intellectual knowledge and their personal growth. To supplement language learning, digital technologies and instruments such as television, language labs, and a variety of designed media, use of audiovisual devices, monitors, and computer keyboards are used to make learning effective (Ahdian, 2007, Xu et al. 2019).

Some researchers such as Sung, Cheng and Liu (2016) and Lee (2010) are in favour of technology based language learning, while other researchers such as Lipsey and Wilson (2001), Norris and Ortega (2000), and Oswald and Plonsky (2010) have expressed doubts about its success. The greatest hindrance to apply technology in English classes are the limited resources, teacher's skills, feeling and attitude towards ICT and the type of application and software available (Mumtaz, 2000; Adams & Newton, 2009; Littlewood, 2007) .

Though there is already an agreement on its effectiveness, there are certain constrains like turn-taking which leads to minimalization and indexicality to perform particular language task, too many clarification and comprehension checks, confirmation checks, and self-repetition during language task performance which have less facilitative role in second language acquisition (Seedhouse, 1999). TBLT considers the context that is narrowly attributed to linguistic and pragmatic features of language and it also fails to include broader social, political, historical, and cultural aspects (Kumaravadivelu 2006).

Intercultural Approach:

Due to less attention in the cultural aspect by most of English language teaching approaches, many researchers (Byram 1997; Byram et al. 2002; Corbett 2022; Kramersch 1998; Kramersch and Sullivan 1996; Liddicoat et al. 1999; St Clair and Phipps 2008) advocated for an intercultural approach to language learning. The primary objective of this approach is to create 'learners as intercultural speakers or mediators who are able to engage with various complexity and multiple identities which will help them to avoid the stereotyping notion of perceiving someone through a single identity (Byram et al. 2002). It also aims to prepare learners interacting with people of other culture and be able to accept them with their unique characteristics, behaviors, and values. One framework that supports this innovation is the Council of Europe's Common European Framework of Reference aiming to help learners interact with the speakers of other languages on equal and balanced terms and to be aware of their own identities (Byram et al. 2002).

Indeed, this approach is not free from problems. The approach and its objectives are difficult to realize in classroom, immersion, and independent learning contexts as it lacks specificity (Wang and Coleman, 2009). As a result, this method is underscored as it is more likely to experience technical and practical limitations for real life classroom.

Post method Pedagogy:

Too much emphasis on methods and approaches have led to another major transition in ELT that is from methods to beyond methods (Richards 1990) which is to the post method condition (Kumaravadivelu, 1994). Post method condition refers to that compels us to refigure the relationship between the theorizers and the practitioners in English language classroom. This pedagogy is shaped by the three dimensional principles of particularity, practicality and possibility. It is rooted from eclecticism (Akbari, 2008) and failures in the use of past methods (Pennycook 1989; Prahbu 1990). Prahbu (1990) confirmed that there is no best method to teach language, what matters is the teachers' personal conceptualization of what will make their learners to learn. It allows the power to the practitioners (teachers) to develop classroom oriented theories of practice based on their informed teaching, experience, and critical appraisal. Maximum choice of alternatives and research based pedagogy emerged multilingual pedagogy, critical pedagogy, translanguaging and plurilingualism in practice. It took teacher cognition, reasoning and beliefs in to account to choose and imply appropriate alternative teaching strategies to language.

However, this post method pedagogy is not without weaknesses. Some scholars (Larsen-Freeman 2005 and Liu 1995) affirmed that post method is not an alternative to method but an additional method only based on practitioners assumptions without any authentic logical bases of classroom pedagogy. Bell, 2003 argued that it is just a synthesis of different methods under CLT ignoring the teaching and language teacher realities (Akbari, 2008) which only suggests that methods have limitations which must be overcome.

Discussion

All the pedagogies for teaching English have been presented as Traditional or classical and New or modern from the evolution or time perspective. Though there exist some difference between these broad categories of pedagogies but it is seen that new pedagogies also uses some essential components of traditional pedagogies. For example though decoding of meaning of words is essential in both types of pedagogies but it is the most important aspect of classical pedagogy. Secondly, the traditional or classical pedagogy are based on behaviouristic and cognitive school of thought, on the other hand recent or modern English pedagogies are based on constructivist and post positivism thoughts. Linked with these foundational perspectives, it can be stated that as remembering and cramming are medium of language learning, the teachers and text book are highly focused in classical pedagogies. On the other hand in the modern or recent pedagogies which are activity centric learning process, the learners occupy the central position in the learning process. Thirdly, in the traditional English pedagogies during learning of English, learning about own socio-cultural context was given less value rather value was on native speaker's way of communication, life and culture but academicians claim that in modern English pedagogies, inter and multi-cultural perspective was given priority. As a result in English lesson, the contents were primarily based on English literature of Western world which were taught in classical methods school of thought.

These pedagogies are not against each other rather they have their own application context. For example, as Traditional pedagogies give more focus on grammatical rules or structure of language which are very much required for written context but as recent pedagogies give more importance

on functional or communicative aspects, these are required for development of communication and pragmatics.

Conclusion:

Lots of similarities are seen in the classroom practices and some strategies of both conventional and modern pedagogy. It can be stated that, the amalgam of the traditional and new techniques are being employed in schools located in urban areas, where as the traditional methods of teaching language are still being practiced in rural areas. Now the question arises whether these changes and variations in pedagogies can be called as a transition or transformation. From a developmental perspective it may be said as transition because of the multiplicity of methods and introduction of new classroom strategies and student engagement practices. The goals of English learning became dynamic and contextual with respect to its use and global exposure along with integration of technology. It can be considered that the current trend of language teaching methodology is the blend of what was practiced in the past and what we are currently doing. The traditional methods serve as the subsequent guides the current.

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